

Traceability of samples and data in multi-organizational environments with the Common Provenance Framework

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SUMMARY

Reproducibility issues are widely reported in science. As a response, scientific communities have called for enhanced provenance information documenting the complete research life cycle, from biological or environmental material acquisition to translating research results into practice. In this work, we present the Common Provenance Framework (CPF), a domain-agnostic, integrative framework for provenance in multi-organizational environments, with the aim to advance quality assessment of research outputs. Based on formulated requirements, the framework consists of a unified terminology, a multi-organizational provenance architecture, a non-repudiation policy, a PROV-based data model, and a reference implementation. The CPF enables querying of provenance that is generated and managed independently by different organizations, while providing mechanisms to preserve confidentiality and trustworthiness of information. The CPF serves as an open foundation for the ISO 23494 provenance standard series, and is relevant to various international initiatives.

DSML 3: Development/Pre-production. The Common Provenance Framework has been designed and piloted across multiple distinct research domains including digital pathology, infectious disease data management, bioprocessing digital twins, and computational workflow provenance. It is being adopted by the BBMRI-ERIC biobanking infrastructure and UNCAN-Connect platform, and forms the technical basis for the ISO 23494 provenance standard series.

KEYWORDS

Provenance, traceability, reproducibility, Common Provenance Framework, Common Provenance Model, ISO 23494, W3C PROV

BIGGER PICTURE

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The validity of any research result depends on the history of the inputs from which it was derived. For instance, a clinical trial outcome depends on how patient samples were collected and processed. A trained AI model depends on the characteristics of every dataset and specimen that contributed to its training data. An epidemiological conclusion depends on the methods applied at each stage of data generation and integration. In modern research, this information routinely crosses organizational boundaries – samples move from hospitals to laboratories, data moves from measurement facilities to analysis centers, and results are integrated across institutions operating under different protocols and governance frameworks. With each new organization involved, the chain of dependencies becomes harder to trace. There is currently no decentralized general solution that makes the full provenance of the results traversable and trustworthy across independently operating organizations.

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The FAIR data principles – widely adopted as reference guidelines for scientific data management – require that data be associated with detailed provenance, but this requirement was designed for single repositories and does not extend across organizational boundaries. The Common Provenance Framework (CPF) fills this gap: it provides the shared infrastructure layer that allows each organization to record and manage its own provenance independently, while making the full chain traversable and verifiable from end to end. The need is especially acute for AI systems, where a model’s fitness for purpose depends on the complete history of its training data – a dependency that is invisible without cross-organizational provenance. Validated across life sciences, the CPF is domain-agnostic. As data governance frameworks globally increasingly mandate documentation of data lineage, standardized cross-organizational provenance infrastructure will become both a scientific and legal necessity. The CPF provides a concrete, open foundation for this.

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INTRODUCTION

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The ability to verify scientific findings is essential to research, as new progress typically builds upon earlier work and requires confirmation of existing findings¹. *Reproducibility* is the ability to check results of an experiment by running it again, and constitutes a realization of fitness for purpose, which is, in essence, the realization of quality assessment as defined in quality standards². Regardless of whether a result is fully reproducible, traceability through associated documentation is often a precursor for reproducibility or quality analysis. Such documentation contains information about how a result was obtained, how long an experiment took, or which algorithms were used during computation or analysis. The trustworthiness of this documentation enables informed decisions about subsequent use and adoption of results, as it provides guarantees that the information is authentic, truthful, and not fabricated.

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Problems with the quality, trustworthiness, and reproducibility of research results have been repeatedly reported in science^{1,3–10}, with impacts on health, economics, and political decision-making^{11–14}. Poor documentation of data sources, such as specimens or analytical procedures from which the data were generated, is a significant contributing factor. Consequently, professional societies and researchers have called for improved and standardized documentation of data, their sources, and the methods used in research studies^{15–19}.

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Provenance is information about the history of an object throughout its lifetime²⁰. The adoption of provenance has been explored in scientific domains to support traceable lineage of entities such as biological material, workflows, or data. The purpose of provenance adoption varies – for instance, to support the replication of conducted experiments^{21,22}, to assess

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the quality of data²³ or biological material²⁴, or to support accountability in complex systems with cross-organizational boundaries²⁵. Provenance information may be represented in multiple ways, including software logs, metadata schemas, or dedicated documentation. A common representation is an oriented graph in which nodes represent objects, processes, or agents, and edges represent the relations between them^{26,27}. W3C PROV²⁸, the dominant standard for provenance representation, defines a data model and associated serialization formats and ontology, and provides building blocks for achieving provenance interoperability – the ability to exchange provenance across organizational boundaries, interpret it consistently, and do so in heterogeneous environments. However, PROV alone does not ensure interoperability in the operational sense required for multi-organizational traceability.

Often, the overall provenance information must document a chain of objects derived one from another, such as data derived from samples, or AI models trained on data. The documentation spans across multiple organizations, such as laboratories or research infrastructures. When this chain crosses organizational boundaries – as is common in current research – each organization can typically provide provenance only about the part of an object’s life cycle that was under its control²⁹. Because the quality of a resulting object (e.g., a trained AI model) depends on the quality of all its precursors (e.g., the datasets used for training and the samples from which the data were derived), assessing its quality depends on the traceability of the required information. The challenge in these cases is not the fragmentation of provenance itself, but the absence of harmonized, traversable, trust- and confidentiality-preserving links between these fragments. This, in turn, requires the ability to locate, integrate, and query the provenance of all precursors, potentially spanning multiple organizations and domains. To enable this, provenance must be represented in an interoperable and machine-actionable way, its exchange across organizational boundaries must be supported, confidential parts of the chain must be protectable, and the integrity and authenticity of provenance must be verifiable – including for parts of the chain that are not directly accessible.

This work addresses the lack of a comprehensive decentralized provenance framework supporting traceability in multi-organizational environments by defining the Common Provenance Framework (CPF). The CPF is a domain-agnostic, integrative framework for multi-organizational and cross-domain provenance. It defines unified terminology to support provenance management and a multi-organizational provenance architecture prescribing a mechanism for integration with existing systems, and a standardized data model to support interoperability. The CPF addresses bidirectional traceability and interoperability of provenance, and supports confidentiality and non-repudiation of origin of provenance. A comprehensive analysis of how the integration of described objects, their provenance, and additional provenance metadata affects each other resulted in *Provenance Exchange Schemes* – a conceptualization of approaches for their exchange. The CPF builds on W3C PROV-DM²⁷. A reference software implementation of the framework was developed to support the evaluation presented in this work. The CPF is the main building block of the *ISO 23494 Provenance information model for biological material and data* standard series³⁰, developed in ISO Technical Committee 276 Biotechnology Working Group 5 Data Processing and Integration.

The CPF has been developed and validated across a broad range of domains, demonstrating its domain-agnostic character. The primary development was performed on a complex AI pipeline in digital pathology^{29,31}, which includes all of the challenges underlying the problem statement of this work. Beyond this primary use case, the framework has been developed in the context of computational workflow provenance based on Research Object Crates³², industrial biotechnology³³, clinical decision support systems³⁴, or infectious diseases data³⁵. Although the framework has been developed recently, it is already being

adopted by BBMRI-ERIC¹, the European biobanking infrastructure, the UNCAN-Connect cancer research platform², and the Czech national implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC CZ)³. Beyond specific deployments, the CPF is relevant to major international data governance and AI accountability initiatives and regulations. These may include, for instance, the European Health Data Space and EU AI Act in Europe, or the NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy and NIST AI Risk Management Framework in the United States, all of which mandate documentation of data provenance or AI training data lineage across organizational boundaries.

This manuscript is structured as follows. The Results section presents an overview of the framework and its evaluation, which assesses the ability of the framework to meet formulated requirements against a real-world multi-organizational provenance chain using a set of targeted provenance queries. The Discussion and Related Work sections follow. The Methods section describes the development process. Supplementary material S1 provides the full technical specification of the framework. Supplementary material S2 contains the source code and data used for the evaluation.

RESULTS

This work presents the following results:

1. **Formulation of general requirements** on a multi-organizational provenance, which are derived from existing provenance systems and architectures.
2. **The Common Provenance Framework** – an integrative, domain-agnostic framework addressing the general requirements, comprising five primary contributions:
 - a harmonized **terminology** for multi-organizational provenance;
 - a software architecture for independently operated provenance stores;
 - the **Common Provenance Model (CPM)**, PROV-DM-based data model, which is the core of the presented framework;
 - a **non-repudiation policy** for provenance information, formulated independently of domain and legal environment;
 - **Provenance Exchange Schemes**, a novel categorization of how described objects, their provenance, and provenance metadata can be exchanged between organizations.

The CPF is supported by a generic chain-traversal algorithm and a reference implementation. The results are described in detail in the Supplementary material S1.

3. **Evaluation of the CPF** on a digital-pathology provenance chain, testing four expectations – functional compliance, scalability of traversal, confidentiality, and trustworthiness.

¹<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/scientific-collaboration/wp1-acceleration-of-datafication-of-biobanks-and-biomolecular-resources-to-enable-reproducible-advanced-medical-research-wp1/>

²<https://uncan-connect.eu/>

³<https://www.eosc.cz/en/about-eosc-cz/initiative-eosc-cz>

Motivating Example

The following example illustrates why cross-organizational provenance traceability is necessary for quality assessment and what kinds of information it is expected to provide.

Digital pathology applies advances in imaging technologies and machine learning to develop systems capable of diagnosing or supporting patient diagnosis based on clinical data and high-resolution scans of histopathological biological material, also called Whole Slide Images (WSIs). This use case provides a solid and complex pipeline requiring the documentation of both physical (samples) and digital (data, AI models) objects, and includes a wide range of heterogeneous processes (sample acquisition, processing, storage, data generation, data processing using AI models) carried out in a heterogeneous multi-organizational environment.

The example includes three types of organizations: a hospital, where biological samples are collected from patients and sent for examination; a pathology laboratory, where samples are processed, stained with chemical agents, and scanned to produce WSIs; and an AI research group based at a university, where WSIs are preprocessed, used to train AI models for detecting tissue structures, and evaluated. The quality of the resulting trained AI model depends on the characteristics of all its precursors and the steps that led to its development. For instance, the staining protocol applied during tissue preparation is absolutely critical for both model training and inference: the same dye binds to different molecular structures depending on the immuno-agents used, meaning that an AI model trained on data from one staining protocol may produce invalid inferences when applied to slides prepared under a different protocol. Such parameter-level dependencies between steps performed by different organizations are invisible unless provenance is traceable across the entire chain.

Consider the following demonstrative questions related to a trained model from digital pathology.

1. Given a trained model, what is the number of patients providing the data, while different facilities can hand patients over and patients may be examined multiple times at a single facility?
2. Given a trained model, can we prove that the data of the same patient is not in both the training and validation datasets?
3. Given a trained model, how is it ensured that the validation and training datasets do not contain images from the same patients, presuming that data or patients can be shared by different organizations?
4. Given a trained model, have compatible staining protocols been used during training?
5. Given a trained model, in the case of inference, is the staining and scanning protocol compatible with the protocols used for training?
6. Given a trained model, how many devices were used to generate the image data in the validation dataset?
7. Given a trained model, from how many facilities does the validation dataset come?
8. Given a trained model, how many pathologists annotated the image data in the validation dataset?

Having answers to these questions contributes to the assessment of the quality of the resulting model. The main challenge for effective traceability is that different institutions hold

different parts of the information. For example, the organization integrating datasets knows 214
how many facilities contributed data; laboratories know which devices and pathologists were 215
involved; and hospitals know the patients from whom samples were taken – details that labo- 216
ratories typically do not have and which may reveal personal information. This demonstrates 217
that answering the questions requires provenance from multiple organizations, which must 218
be traversable in a unified, trust- and confidentiality-preserving manner. 219

General Requirements on Multi-organizational Provenance 220

The following requirements on a multi-organizational provenance framework are grounded in 221
an analysis of existing provenance systems and architectures^{36–39}, which are also underlined 222
by the motivating example. 223

- **R1: Architecture for multi-organizational provenance.** Automated traversal of a 224
provenance chain requires a uniform architecture for a multi-organizational provenance 225
framework. 226
- **R2: Multi-organizational retrieval.** The resulting framework must take into consider- 227
ation the characteristics of the exchange of described objects, provenance, and prove- 228
nance metadata. 229
- **R3: Consistent Terminology and Semantics.** As the understanding and interpreta- 230
tion of the term “provenance” varies across multiple domains^{40–43}, it is essential that 231
the understanding of related terms is harmonized in a multi-organizational environ- 232
ment, so that different domains do not deal with different concepts despite using the 233
same terms. 234
- **R4: Provenance interoperability.** Automated traversal of a provenance chain re- 235
quires an interoperable data model so that provenance – especially the links between 236
distributed provenance pieces and provenance metadata – can be consistently inter- 237
preted. 238
- **R5: Robustness.** The framework must address situations when a piece of provenance 239
is missing, e.g., because an organization has not generated provenance in accordance 240
with predefined specifications, or has not generated any provenance at all. 241
- **R6: Confidentiality.** The resulting provenance framework must enable protection of 242
confidential information and personal privacy⁴⁴, e.g., by intentionally breaking a prove- 243
nance chain. 244
- **R7: Integrity and non-repudiation.** An error can occur during provenance gener- 245
ation^{45,46}, and provenance might be accidentally or intentionally modified^{45–48}. The 246
resulting provenance framework must enable integrity and non-repudiation of prove- 247
nance, both for accessible and for hidden parts of the provenance chain. 248
- **R8: Integrability.** The solution must be designed to easily integrate with existing 249
domain-specific approaches³⁸, so that it is flexible enough to cover a wide range of 250
use cases. 251

The Common Provenance Framework

The CPF is a domain-agnostic framework for multi-organizational provenance addressing R1–R8. The following paragraphs provide an overview of the framework, while detailed technical description is provided in supplementary S1.

Provenance chain formation

Each involved organization collects provenance about the objects it handles and transforms it, during a *finalization event*, into a standardized, immutable package called a *finalized provenance component* (FPC). A *described object* – the physical or digital object being traced, such as a biological sample, a dataset, or a trained AI model – is documented by FPCs spanning its full life cycle across organizations. Each FPC is assigned a globally unique persistent identifier and can be linked to the FPCs that precede and follow it in the chain, forming a *provenance chain*. Backward links (to the preceding FPC) are mandatory; forward links (to subsequent FPCs) are optional, as they require notifying respective organization when a new FPC is created.

Metadata about each FPC, including versioning information and non-repudiation evidence, is stored separately in a *meta-component*. This separation keeps the FPC itself immutable while allowing metadata to be updated, combined across multiple FPCs, or extended with new information without altering provenance content. Figure 1 illustrates a provenance chain in which each organization independently manages its FPCs while linking them to the chain.

Figure 1: Schema of a provenance chain composed of finalized provenance components.

The Common Provenance Model

The CPM is the underlying data model of the CPF. Its key contribution is the separation, within each FPC, of a minimal *traversal information* from *domain-specific* provenance. The traversal information has a strictly prescribed structure: it identifies the described objects received as inputs and produced as outputs of a documented activity, and carries the links to preceding and following FPCs in the chain. Domain-specific provenance – capturing the details of what occurred during an activity – is attached alongside the traversal structure as an extension. This separation enables a generic, domain-agnostic traversal algorithm

regardless of the particular processes or objects documented, supports finer-grained access control at the boundary between traversal and domain-specific content, which aligns with the least privilege principle⁴⁹ by allowing chain traversal without exposing unnecessary information.

The idea of separating traversal information from domain-specific provenance had been introduced in our earlier work²⁹ before it was subsequently refined through multiple European research projects and use cases^{35,50,51}. The version presented here constitutes the final version of the CPM and its integration with the complete CPF – including the multi-organizational architecture, the non-repudiation policy, and the Provenance Exchange Schemes. The CPM further specifies a redundancy mechanism to support robustness when parts of a provenance chain are lost or corrupted, or intermediate organizations in a chain do not generate provenance at all. The CPM also defines how meta-components can be extended to carry non-repudiation evidence. The full CPM specification and a generic traversal algorithm are provided in Supplementary S1.

Non-repudiation of provenance origin

In multi-organizational settings, provenance must be not only tamper-evident but also *non-repudiable*: no party, including the organization that originally generated an FPC, should be able to deny having produced it. This matters because an organization providing provenance could have a motive to alter, withhold, or delete evidence if harm has been caused later – for instance, a dataset claimed to be generated as part of a clinical trial is later proven fabricated (e.g., see the Surgisphere case⁵²). A digital signature alone is insufficient for non-repudiation in the long term, as it does not confirm when it was created, whether the keys were valid at that time, or whether they were later compromised. The CPF therefore defines a *non-repudiation policy* specifying requirements on evidence generation, trusted timestamping, independent evidence storage, and long-term key management. This policy is primarily based on general requirements on irrefutable evidence⁵³, ISO 13888⁵⁴, and our prior research³⁴.

Evaluation of the CPF

The evaluation of the framework is designed around four expectations derived from the general requirements and tested using experiments with targeted provenance queries.

Expectations

1. **H1: Compliance with functional requirements.** The framework’s ability to trace requested information in a provenance chain in both backward and forward directions, using a unified traversal algorithm, allowing multiple versions of a finalized provenance component.
2. **H2: Scalability.** The framework’s ability to perform better in traversal using CPM features compared to a pure PROV-based solution, tested with respect to the size of the domain-specific provenance graphs.
3. **H3: Partial confidentiality.** The framework’s ability to trace requested information for which the user is authorized, and not to trace requested information when the user is not authorized.

4. **H4: Trustworthiness.** The framework’s ability to enable the verification of the integrity and authenticity of both accessible and hidden provenance subgraphs. 321
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Provenance Chain for Evaluation 323

The expectations are tested on a provenance chain designed for the digital pathology pipeline. 324
The chain comprises five types of finalized provenance components, which are depicted in 325
Figure 2. 326

1. **Sample acquisition FPC** documents the sample acquisition process. As the beginning of the provenance chain, it contains no backward links. Patients are documented only in the domain-specific part. A separate FPC is created for each sample. 327
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2. **Sample processing and image generation FPC** documents sample processing and WSI generation. A separate FPC is created for each sample. 330
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3. **Data preprocessing FPC** documents aggregation and conversion of WSIs into a dataset (training or validation). Both datasets are documented in a separate FPC. 332
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4. **AI model training FPC** documents AI model training, with the training dataset as input and a trained model as output. 334
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5. **AI model evaluation FPC** documents the model evaluation, taking the validation dataset and the trained model as inputs, and producing an HTML report containing tested metrics as output. 336
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Queries 339

The queries are designed to test the expectations and to demonstrate the framework’s ability to address the requirements R1–R8. The queries are derived from the demonstrative questions posed in the motivating example. 340
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1. **Q1 (intra-component traceability):** Given a trained model, return all WSI identifiers that were used for model training. 343
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2. **Q2 (subsequent components backward traceability):** Given the training dataset, return all sample identifiers from which the dataset was generated. 345
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3. **Q3 (subsequent components forward traceability):** Given a sample identifier, return all WSI identifiers that were generated from the sample. 347
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4. **Q4.1 (non-subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, return all sample identifiers used to train the model. 349
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5. **Q4.2 (subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, how many devices were used to generate the image data in the training dataset? 351
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6. **Q4.3 (non-subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, how many facilities were involved in the procurement of the training dataset? 353
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7. **Q4.4 (subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, how many pathologists annotated the image data in the training dataset? 355
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Figure 2: Structure of the provenance chain for the framework evaluation.

8. **Q4.5 (non-subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, what is the number of patients providing the training data (while different facilities can hand patients over, and chronic patients may be included multiple times at a single facility)? 357
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9. **Q4.6 (non-subsequent components backward traceability):** Given a trained model, how is it ensured that the testing and training datasets do not contain images from the same patients (presuming that data or patients can be “shared” by different organizations providing the data)? 361
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10. **Q5 (non-subsequent components forward traceability):** Given an acquired sample, return all AI model identifiers that were trained on data generated from the sample. 365
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11. **Q6 (confidential information):** Given a trained model, return a list of the patient identifiers whose samples were used during the training process. 367
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12. **Q7 (non-repudiable authenticity information):** Given a trained model, confirm that the provenance chain documenting all the model precursors is authentic, even for the hidden components. 369
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13. **Q-SCALE (intra-component forward-to-backward connector traceability):** Given a trained model, return the identifier of the dataset used for training. 372
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The mapping between the expectations, experiments, and the queries is shown in Table 1.

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Table 1: Mapping between expectations, experiments, and queries.

Expectation	Experiment	Queries
H1	E1	Q1–Q5
H2	E2	Q-SCALE
H3	E3	Q4.1, Q5, Q6
H4	E4	Q7

Experiments and Results

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Experiments E1, E3, and E4 test H1, H3, and H4 qualitatively by verifying that queries return the expected results. The expected values are determined during instantiation of the evaluation environment, and can be manually compared to query results, as depicted in Figure 3. E1 confirms H1: all information requested by Q1–Q5 is traceable. E3 confirms H3: Q4.1 and Q5 return the requested information using redundant connectors despite the hidden component, while Q6 correctly returns no patient identifiers, as the component holding them is hidden. E4 confirms H4: Q7 verifies the authenticity of all components in the chain, including hidden ones, via the Trusted Party Service.

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(dbprov) jodo@sandbox:~/workspace/ics-muni/dbprov$ python -m experiments.queries.query_3_0_sample_to_wsi
Provenance traversal retrieved 2 unique WSIs from the sample:

/dbprov/data/CAMELYON16/training/normal/normal_019.tif /dbprov/data/CAMELYON16/training/normal/normal_060.tif

Expected result retrieved from DB:

/dbprov/data/CAMELYON16/training/normal/normal_019.tif /dbprov/data/CAMELYON16/training/normal/normal_060.tif
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Figure 3: Example of a query response.

Experiment E2 tests H2 quantitatively by comparing traversal response times over CPM-based versus pure PROV-DM provenance graphs, with a scaling factor representing the length of the shortest derivation path crossing the domain-specific part of the graph. Figure 4 shows that response times for CPM-based traversal are lower than those for a pure PROV-DM graph. This is expected: with growing size of the domain-specific part and fixed size of the traversal information, the length of derivation paths in the traversal information remains constant, while the PROV-DM traversal must search the growing graph. The degree of how much the response time grows is dependent on the structure of the domain-specific graph.

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Of the eight requirements R1–R8, the CPF addresses all eight. In particular, it is the first framework to address all the requirements simultaneously within a unified multi-organizational provenance framework.

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DISCUSSION

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Generalization to other domains

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Similarly to the motivating example, the same dependency structure recurs wherever multi-step research pipelines cross organizational boundaries to produce training data for AI models, which is why the CPF is designed to be domain-agnostic. For instance, in environmental

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Figure 4: Q-SCALE response times with growing shortest derivation path length crossing the domain-specific part of a provenance graph.

science, eDNA metabarcoding pipelines span field sampling teams, sequencing laboratories, and bioinformatics groups; the choice of primer sequences and filtration method at the sampling stage determines which organisms' DNA is captured and amplified, directly shaping the taxonomic composition of datasets on which AI classifiers are trained⁵⁵. In pharmaceutical manufacturing, digital twins for bioreactor control are trained on data generated across cell line development, cultivation, and downstream characterization; bioreactor conditions such as pH, temperature profile, and feeding strategy are critical process parameters that determine product quality attributes, meaning a digital twin trained on one process configuration may not generalize to a different scale or setup⁵⁶. In materials science, AI models for property prediction draw on data from raw material procurement, synthesis under controlled conditions, and multi-technique characterization across different facilities; synthesis parameters such as temperature profiles, atmosphere, and precursor purity determine the resulting microstructure and phase composition, so a model trained on data from one synthesis route may not transfer to samples produced under different conditions⁵⁷. In each case, answering questions about an AI model's validity and quality requires provenance that is traversable across all steps and organizations.

Multi-organizational properties

The CPF addresses all four properties required for a multi-organizational provenance architecture, which were defined in a prior work³⁶.

1. *Scalability*: the CPF imposes no limit on the number of organizations in a provenance chain.
2. *Agility*: enabling backward traceability does not require existing participants to change software or have knowledge of new participants, enabling forward traceability requires

only that a sender be notified when a downstream receiver creates a new finalized provenance component. 424
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3. *Autonomy*: each organization independently controls its own finalized provenance components, including access control decisions. Access can be further refined by applying a graph-transformation procedure before content is served to a user. 426
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4. *Resilience*: failure of a single provenance store does not affect the availability of others; robustness is additionally supported by the connector redundancy mechanism in the CPM, and – when persistent identifiers are used – by the inherent redundancy of PID resolution infrastructures. 429
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Adoption considerations 433

The adoption of the CPF by an organization is a relatively straightforward task and can be carried out in multiple steps: (1) determination of objects and processes to be covered by the CPF, directly deriving from the goals of the organization in provenance tracking; (2) modeling of required information according to the CPM; (3) implementation of the finalization event to translate provenance information into the standardized representation; (4) storage and maintenance of the standardized provenance; (5) implementation of access to standardized provenance for relevant users. The ease of adoption depends on the scope and complexity of individual organizations and documented processes. Compared with full adoption of PROV, the CPM can be easier to adopt, as adopters can use only the traversal information and are not required to design the structure of the underlying domain-specific provenance. Keeping just the traversal information enables traceability of information about executed processes, their inputs, outputs, and associated metadata in multi-organizational environments. The adoption without a domain-specific part does not require extensive knowledge of PROV, which may otherwise be a barrier to adoption. 434
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One anticipated challenge is that full advantage of the framework requires adoption by the whole chain of organizations involved in a documented object's life cycle⁴³. This is not specific to the CPF but applies to any multi-organizational framework. Starting the deployment locally and then building out the distributed solution is the recommended approach. Research infrastructures can be good starting points, as they span a wide range of organizations and processes and can provide services and capacities to help member organizations implement the framework. 448
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An open architectural question for the adoption of the framework is related to the need to build an additional level of infrastructure to store and manage finalized provenance components, which must be sustained in the long term⁵⁸. Three basic options exist: (1) a separate dedicated provenance storage system, as presented in this work; (2) provenance expressed as part of an object's metadata in a repository (e.g., as DCAT metadata⁵⁹); or (3) provenance expressed as part of the described object itself (e.g., in a file metadata header). Options (2) and (3) address semantic interoperability but do not directly cover provenance management requirements such as non-repudiation or immutability. Options (1) and (2) provide looser coupling with domain-specific information, which in turn provides more flexibility. Options (2) and (3) were not technically explored as part of this work, but the framework can serve as a foundational starting point for this research direction. 455
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Ethical and legal factors may pose another challenge for automated querying of distributed provenance. Adopting organizations would not necessarily collect more information than they already have – they would transform its relevant part into a harmonized representation and create links enabling traversal. Proper authentication and authorization infrastructure for heterogeneous multi-organizational environments is also required. 466
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Incentives to adopt a distributed provenance framework may play a crucial role. Users of research objects – samples or data – can request provision of standardized provenance. This includes not just researchers assessing the fitness of purpose of an object, but also all intermediate organizations. Adoption of a common framework can provide a competitive advantage: organizations that provide standardized provenance can become preferred suppliers. Incentives such as better funding opportunities, reduced publication costs, or procurement requirements for hardware and software can also play a significant role.

Limitations of the Study

Complexity. The framework integrates results from multiple provenance-related domains, including multi-organizational provenance, interoperability, confidentiality, integrity, and non-repudiation. While it addresses all formulated requirements, its complexity may pose a barrier to users studying and understanding all aspects and their interrelationships. Technical guidelines and recommendations are being developed as part of current adoption projects.

Technical integrability. The reference implementation is provided in Python. Wide adoption will require implementations in additional programming languages and integration with existing systems – such as research software, electronic lab notebooks, and data-generating devices – so that harmonized provenance is collected without placing excessive burden on end users or organizations.

Framing into a legal environment. The non-repudiation policy presented in this work is not bound to a specific legal environment. Feasibility for legally defensible provenance will require adaptation to specific application and legal contexts, which is the subject of ongoing development.

Advanced privacy protection. Confidentiality is addressed primarily through access control at the FPC level and through separation of traversal and domain-specific information. Compatibility with more advanced privacy techniques – encryption, anonymization, zero-knowledge proofs, or differential privacy – was not evaluated. It is up to adopters to define an appropriate level of access control granularity.

Semantic extensions for non-repudiation. The CPM does not yet contain formal semantic definitions (e.g., ontology terms) for integrity and non-repudiation attributes in meta-components such as hash names, digital signatures, or certificate identifiers. These are currently described in a proprietary way and require a standard representation for interoperability in long term.

Future directions

Further adoption and production-ready implementations. Despite being piloted and validated across multiple use cases, large-scale adoption will likely reveal unexplored gaps. Particular focus should be placed on complex, cross-domain research pipelines – for instance, multidisciplinary pipelines combining genomics, climate, and socioeconomics (as witnessed in OneHealth^{60,61}) – or on integration with IoT devices, lab automation devices,

and sensors. Further development should also produce provenance-ready solutions addressing authentication and authorization integration, formal semantic extensions for provenance metadata, and CPM validators.

Trustworthy provenance chain traversal. Future research may explore how integrity or non-repudiation violations propagate through a provenance chain: in which cases is a provenance piece trustworthy if it is referenced from a piece with a corrupted digital signature?

Support for reproducibility and quality assessment. Once enhanced traceability is established, a natural next step is to quantify how much CPF-enabled traceability contributes to reproducibility or FAIRness, as quantitative metrics for both have recently been published^{62,63}.

Legal and regulatory compliance. Provenance is a key mechanism for explainability and auditing. Demonstrating the framework’s applicability in supporting compliance with regulatory frameworks such as the In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation, Medical Device Regulation, or EU AI Act³¹ is a priority for future work.

RELATED WORK

A multi-organizational provenance framework relates to a wide range of areas: provenance interoperability, multi-organizational architectures, provenance confidentiality, and provenance integrity and non-repudiation. The primary gaps lie in architectural support and practical interoperability; confidentiality, integrity, and non-repudiation are well-studied in isolation and are primarily relevant here in terms of their integrability with a multi-organizational framework.

Provenance interoperability

PROV²⁸ is the most comprehensive standard for provenance representation. PROV-DM²⁷ defines a data model serializable into multiple formats^{64–66}, and PROV-O⁶⁷ provides an ontology for semantic interoperability. Domain-specific standards accommodate provenance as part of a broader scope: RO-Crate⁶⁸ packages research artifacts with provenance metadata; FHIR⁶⁹ represents clinical provenance through typed resource properties; environmental research infrastructures proposed PROV-based provenance services^{70,71}; the IVOA Provenance Data Model⁷² extends PROV-DM for astronomy. The Data & Trust Alliance Data Provenance Standards⁴ is a cross-industry metadata schema for responsible AI provenance, now advancing toward OASIS standardization.

However, PROV enables interoperability but does not ensure it^{73,74}: two producers can both be PROV-compliant yet represent the same real-world situation with incompatible structures. No widely adopted specification exists for the *minimal* subset of provenance that must be shared to enable robust cross-organizational traversal under heterogeneous producers. Linking mechanisms and traversal metadata are therefore typically introduced ad hoc within individual systems. Multi-organizational use cases also require interoperability of *provenance metadata* – versioning information, or digital signatures of provenance – yet the co-evolution of provenance and its metadata is rarely treated as a first-class design problem.

⁴<https://www.dtaalliance.org/news/announcing-the-data-provenance-standards-v1-0-0>

Multi-organizational provenance

Several systems support distributed provenance in domains where multi-organizational characteristics arise incidentally from distributed architectures: IoT⁷⁵, federated computing⁷⁶, computational grids^{77,78}, curated databases⁷⁹, or others^{80–82}. These systems are limited by narrow application scope, reliance on centralized storage, or use of provenance models pre-dating PROV-DM. More recent approaches^{43,83,84} remain at the hypothesis and high-level proposal stage.

The only prior general architecture specifically designed for multi-organizational provenance³⁶ stores links between provenance pieces within a distributed overlay network. While effective for discovering provenance of digital objects, it addresses only R1, R5, and R6 of the requirements formulated in this work. It does not address R2 (no conceptualization of provenance and metadata exchange), R3 (no harmonized terminology), R4 (a proprietary pre-PROV data model that limits interoperability⁸⁵), R7 (no non-repudiation policy), or R8 (no integrability mechanism). Its applicability to physical objects is unexplored, as the proposed type of identifiers cannot straightforwardly be computed for physical samples whose identifiers are often unique only within individual organizational systems⁸⁶. The CPF addresses all eight requirements and is the first general framework to address all of them within a single unified solution.

No existing work conceptualizes how the characteristics of described objects, their provenance, and provenance metadata influence each other, and existing terminology does not distinguish legacy provenance from interoperable standardized provenance, which is required for proper formulation of requirements on provenance management life cycle.

Provenance confidentiality

Graph transformation approaches^{44,87} are the most mature mechanism for provenance access control, computing consistent, valid provenance views by applying access rules. PROV-AQ⁸⁸ recommends provenance access control via dereferenceable URIs. Despite this maturity, a standardized framework for provenance confidentiality still has open gaps⁸⁹, particularly the alignment of confidentiality mechanisms with a general multi-organizational provenance framework. The CPF addresses this by managing access control at the FPC level and by separating traversal from domain-specific information, enabling the least privilege principle⁴⁹.

Provenance integrity and non-repudiation

Chained signature schemes^{48,90}, blockchain-based tamper-evident logs^{91,92}, and RDF signing techniques⁹³ address provenance integrity in various settings. However, the available literature conflates authenticity and non-repudiation: most sources describe non-repudiation as established simply by a digital signature, without addressing evidence management required for long-term verifiability. No prior work provides a general non-repudiation policy aligned with a multi-organizational provenance framework. While non-repudiation mechanisms have been previously applied to specific provenance systems in our prior research³⁴, the CPF's non-repudiation policy presented here is the first formulated as a domain- and system-independent policy specifically designed for multi-organizational provenance.

METHODS

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The presented framework is the result of long-term development within large European projects, primarily EOSC-Life⁹⁴, BY-COVID³⁵, BIOINDUSTRY 4.0, and EvolveBBMRI⁹⁵. Other scientific collaborations were established outside these projects. As a result, the framework was developed and piloted on heterogeneous use cases, such as computational workflows based on RO-Crates³², industrial biotechnology³³, clinical decision support systems³⁴, or infectious diseases data³⁵.

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The research methodology combined manual and automated provenance collection carried out in an agile, iterative manner across the use cases. Manual provenance collection concerned designing the underlying data model for specific use cases and manually creating the resulting provenance, with the primary purpose of verifying the data model's wide applicability, gathering feedback, and addressing new requirements. Automated provenance collection concerned implementing transformation procedures that take existing provenance – present in the form of a dedicated provenance documentation, logs, or descriptive metadata – as input and generate harmonized provenance as output. The prototypes created through this process were intended as blueprints for potential production software rather than production systems themselves.

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Full automation was achieved for the data preprocessing, AI model training, and AI model evaluation steps of the digital pathology use case, as these were technically integrated with the RationAI⁵ group infrastructure at Masaryk University⁶. Provenance for the sample acquisition and examination steps was generated semi-automatically, using static test data provided by the hospital and biobanking information systems, as direct access to those systems was not available.

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RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

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Lead contact

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Requests for further information and resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Rudolf Wittner (wittner@ics.muni.cz).

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Materials availability

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This study did not generate new materials.

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Data and code availability

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1. **Deposited code/data.** The initial work presented in this paper was previously published as part of a preprint⁹⁶, which focused solely on the exchange schemes and conceptualization of linking between provenance and its metadata. The original manuscript was later revised to include the presentation of the whole distributed provenance framework. Preprint of this manuscript, the supplementary document, the code, and all related data have been deposited at Zenodo and are publicly available⁹⁷. These are also attached to this publication as supplementary files S1 (the supplementary document) and S2 (the code and evaluation).

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⁵<https://rationai.fi.muni.cz/>

⁶<https://www.muni.cz/w>

2. **External repository links.** The code and evaluation (S2) are maintained at <https://gitlab.ics.muni.cz/422328/dbprov>. The CPF implementations will be sustained in long term at <https://github.com/Common-Provenance-Framework>.
3. **Dataset used.** This paper uses a subset of an existing, publicly available dataset⁹⁸ – the CAMELYON dataset.

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The provenance storage system was first implemented as an excellent master thesis by David Gajdoš at the Masaryk University under the supervision of the main author of this manuscript. The implementation was then further developed as part of the pivotal deployment at the RationAI group at the Masaryk University.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

R.W.: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. M.G.: Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. L.P., S.L., C.M., F.F., M.P., N.E., S.S.-R., H.M., J.G., P.H.: Writing – review & editing. J.G., H.M., P.H.: Supervision. L.P., F.F., P.H., J.G., H.M.: Funding acquisition.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES

During the preparation of this work the authors used Claude, ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to enhance the writing style and the structure of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION INDEX

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S1: CPF-article-supplementary.pdf – supplementary document containing detailed descriptions of the Common Provenance Framework (CPF).

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S2: Code-and-evaluation.zip – all related source code. Details of the .zip file are described in the README.md file.

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